

Solvent-free Knoevenagel condensation reaction under microwave irradiation exploiting a new reagent : antimony trichloride

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A rapid microwave-assisted Knoevenagel condensation exploiting antimony trichloride under solvent-free condition is reported. Several aromatic aldehydes condense with malononitrile and ethyl cyanoacetate within a few minutes in high yields.

The present work emphasises the use of inorganic reagents in solvent-free condition, with higher selectivity than similar reactions using organic reagents in organic solvent. The rate of the reaction also plays an important role in the synthesis. The wide applicability of microwave irradiation¹ in chemical reaction enhancement is the manifestation of this fact. Absence of organic solvent detrimental to environment has also been avoided in these synthesis².

Results and discussion

The strategy adopted is to carry out the Knoevenagel condensation of aromatic aldehydes with malononitrile and ethyl cyanoacetate separately using a new reagent – antimony trichloride under microwave irradiation without any organic solvent (Scheme 1) to avoid the hazardous effect to

Scheme 1

solvent-waste. The reactions proceed in good yields within a few minutes (Table 1). The optimum ratio of substrate to reagent is found to be 1 : 1 (molar). The lower amount of reagent results in lower yields due to incomplete reaction. The active methylene compounds selected for this reaction are malononitrile and ethyl cyanoacetate as the cyano compounds act as very good synthons³ in several synthesis. The Knoevenagel condensation products of malononitrile are the precursors of several carbocycles, heterocycles, thiopyran and thiopyridone and C₁₉-gibberellins (plant growth hormones). The reaction products of ethyl cyanoacetate have

been utilized for the synthesis of cyanocoumarins, mercaptopyrimidine as an intermediate for an antimetabolite, as substrates for Guareshit reaction and in the synthesis of diterpene alkaloid. Although a large number of organic reactions has been carried out in the presence of antimony pentachloride⁴ and pentafluoride as reagents, little attention has been concentrated to the exploitation of antimony trichloride⁵ in organic synthesis. In continuation of our ongoing programme⁶ for the application of inorganic reagents as synthetic protocols in organic reactions, we would like to explore the viability of antimony trichloride in the new horizon of organic synthesis. In connection with microwave-induced organic reaction enhancement (MORE) chemistry under solvent-free condition⁶, we report here the Knoevenagel condensation of various aromatic aldehydes with malononitrile and ethyl cyanoacetate using antimony trichloride as condensing agent under microwave irradiation.

The condensation products of ethyl cyanoacetate are single geometric isomer but the unambiguous stereochemical assignment could not be made readily. The time period of the reactions and the high yields reflect the effectiveness of microwave irradiation in formation of cleaner products by minimising the formation of byproducts. Moreover the operational simplicity is one of the causes of wide-spread application of microwave oven.

Experimental

IR spectra were run on Perkin-Elmer FTIR-RXI spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR were determined in d-chloroform solution on Bruker AM300L operating at 300 MHz and re-

Table 1.

Entry	Substrate	Product*	A		B	
			Time (min)	Yield (%)	Time (min)	Yield (%)
1			3.5	92	3	88
2			2	97	3	87
3			2	80	2	88
4			2	70	1.5	90
5			7.5	72	2	86
6			1	75	2.5	87
7			2.5	97	2.5	86
8			4	96	2.5	86
9			2	93	3	85
10			1.5	92	2.5	83

* Isolated yield. A : R = CN; B : R = CO₂Et

ported in δ ppm using tetramethylsilane as the internal standard. The reactions were carried out in a domestic microwave oven (BPL, BMO-700T, 2450 MHz).

General procedure : A mixture of aromatic aldehyde (2.0 mmol), malononitrile (0.132 g, 2.0 mmol)/ethyl cyanoacetate (0.258 g, 2.0 mmol) and antimony trichloride (0.456 g, 2.0 mmol) was taken in a 25 ml Erlenmeyer flask and kept over alumina bath (heat sink) inside a domestic microwave oven and irradiated for 1–7.5 min at medium power level (600 W). The reaction was monitored by TLC. The mixture was poured into ice-cold water and extracted with ethyl acetate (3 \times 5 ml) and washed with saturated sodium metabisulphite (2 \times 5 ml). The organic layer was washed with 10% sodium carbonate solution (10 ml) and brine respectively and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Evaporation of the solvent followed by filtration on a short silica gel column afforded the pure desired products which were characterised by IR and ¹H NMR spectra. The ¹H NMR spectral data for the products of the reaction of malononitrile (1A–10A) and ethylcyanoacetate (1B–10B) with aldehydes are given below :

Entry 1A : δ 7.85–7.44 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.32 (1H, s, =CH). Entry 2A : δ 7.91 (2H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, 2'-H, 6'-H), 7.66 (1H, s, =CH), 7.01 (2H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, 3'-H, 5'-H), 3.90 (3H, s, OCH₃). Entry 3A : δ 7.79 (2H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, 2'-H, 6'-H), 7.64 (1H, s, =CH), 7.45 (2H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, 3'-H, 5'-H). Entry

4A : δ 8.40–8.04 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.92 (1H, s, =CH). Entry 5A : δ 8.67 (1H, m, *J* 1.8 Hz, 2'-H), 8.46 (1H, dd, *J* 8.2, 1.8 Hz, 4'-H), 8.29 (1H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, 6'-H), 7.91 (1H, s, =CH), 7.78 (1H, t, *J* 8.2 Hz, 5'-H). Entry 6A : δ 7.66 (1H, d, *J* 2.0 Hz, 2'-H), 7.56 (1H, s, =CH), 7.24 (1H, dd, *J* 8.3, 2.0 Hz, 6'-H), 6.96 (1H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, 5'-H), 3.97 (1H, s, OCH₃). Entry 7A : δ 7.62 (1H, d, *J* 2.2 Hz, 2'-H), 7.59 (1H, s, =CH), 7.32 (1H, dd, *J* 8.4, 2.2 Hz, 6'-H), 6.90 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, 5'-H), 3.93–3.88 (6H, 2 \times s, 2 \times OCH₃). Entry 8A : δ 7.54 (1H, d, *J* 2.1 Hz, 2'-H), 7.53 (1H, s, =CH), 7.25 (1H, dd, *J* 8.2, 2.1 Hz, 6'-H), 6.86 (1H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, 5'-H), 6.02 (2H, s, OCH₂O). Entry 9A : δ 7.41–6.78 (9H, m, Ar-H, =CH), 5.01 (2H, s, OCH₂), 3.79 (3H, s, OCH₃). Entry 10A : δ 7.47–6.82 (9H, m, Ar-H, =CH), 5.10 (2H, s, OCH₂), 3.83 (3H, s, OCH₃). Entry 1B : δ 7.90 (1H, s, =CH), 7.61–7.08 (5H, m, Ar-H), 4.36 (2H, q, *J* 7.2 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 1.40 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, OCH₂CH₃). Entry 2B : δ 8.16 (1H, s, =CH), 7.98 (2H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 6.98 (2H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 4.32 (2H, q, *J* 7.2 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 3.80 (3H, s, OCH₃), 1.34 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, OCH₂CH₃). Entry 3B : δ 8.19 (1H, s, =CH), 7.91 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.46 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, Ar-H), 4.36 (2H, q, *J* 7.1 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 1.37 (3H, t, *J* 7.1 Hz, OCH₂CH₃). Entry 4B : δ 8.27 (2H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 8.22 (1H, s, =CH), 8.05 (2H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 4.21 (2H, q, *J* 7.1 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 1.37 (3H, t, *J* 7.1 Hz, OCH₂CH₃). Entry 5B : δ 8.66 (1H, t, *J* 1.7 Hz, 2'-H), 8.33 (1H, dd, *J* 8.2, 1.7 Hz, 4'-H), 8.25 (1H, s, =CH), 8.18 (1H, m, 6'-H), 7.66 (1H, m, 5'-H), 4.28 (2H, q, *J* 7.1 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 1.30 (3H, t, *J* 7.1 Hz, OCH₂CH₃). Entry 6B : δ 8.06 (1H, s, =CH), 7.76 (1H, s, 2'-H), 7.34 (1H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, Ar-H), 6.91 (1H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, Ar-H), 6.24 (1H, br s, OH), 4.31 (2H, q, *J* 7.1 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 3.91 (3H, s, OCH₃), 1.33 (3H, t, *J* 7.1 Hz, OCH₂CH₃). Entry 7B : δ 8.08 (1H, s, =CH), 7.73 (1H, d, *J* 2.1 Hz, 2'-H), 7.40 (1H, dd, *J* 8.4, 2.0 Hz, 6'-H), 6.87 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, 5'-H), 4.30 (2H, q, *J* 7.1 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 3.89 (6H, s, 2 \times OCH₃), 1.29 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, OCH₂CH₃). Entry 8B : δ 8.04 (1H, s, =CH), 7.63 (1H, d, *J* 1.7 Hz, 2'-H), 7.34 (1H, dd, *J* 8.1, 1.7 Hz, 6'-H), 6.83 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, 5'-H), 6.01 (2H, s, OCH₂O), 4.29 (2H, q, *J* 7.1 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 1.33 (3H, t, *J* 7.1 Hz, OCH₂CH₃). Entry 9B : δ 8.04 (1H, s, =CH), 7.70 (1H, d, *J* 2.1 Hz, 2'-H), 7.44–7.40 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.33 (1H, dd, *J* 8.2, 2.0 Hz, 6'-H), 6.87 (1H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, 5'-H), 5.13 (2H, s, OCH₂), 4.28 (2H, q, *J* 7.1 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 3.88 (3H, s, OCH₃), 1.24 (3H, t, *J* 7.1 Hz, OCH₂CH₃). Entry 10B : δ 8.13 (1H, s, =CH), 7.79 (1H, d, *J* 2.1 Hz, 2'-H), 7.42 (1H, dd, *J* 8.5, 2.1 Hz, 6'-H), 7.38–7.31 (5H, m, Ar-H), 6.94 (1H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, 5'-H), 5.23 (2H, s, OCH₂), 4.35 (2H, q, *J* 7.1 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 3.93 (3H, s, OCH₃), 1.36 (3H, t, *J* 7.1 Hz, OCH₂CH₃).

Note

In conclusion, we have explored the use of antimony trichloride as a condensing agent for Knoevenagel condensation under microwave irradiation in absence of any organic solvent.

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